

How to implement and measure the effects of Robust Design

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"How can your method be implemented in an organisation?"

"What is the cost/benefit of implementing your method?"

Agenda

- Why RD is necessary
- Why RD is not used
- How RD can be used
- The effects of using RD

- ~7 years product development
- ~5 years process development
- ~3 years Ph.D. candidate

Why Robust Design?

Visible costs of non-quality:

- Customer complaints
- In-market service
- Product recalls

Hidden costs of non-quality:

- Rework of inventory and production equipment
- High scrap rates
- Increased quality control
- Launch delays
- Increased R&D costs
- Wrong use of R&D resources
- Tight tolerances
- Variation in performance

R&D Resource Expenditure

Index 100 = Expenditure @ Design Verification

Change Notes

- Analysed 8 projects:
 - 800 Change Notes (Design changes after Design Verification)
 - 65% related to Mechanical Design
 - 63% of Mechanical Change Notes related to Robust Design (41% of total)

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To which extent is RD used in industry

Surveys

Swedish industry
 [Gremyr et al, 2003]

UK industry
 [Araujo, 1996]

US Industry & Military
 [Thornton, 2000]

The extent to which robust design methods are **known** in the Swedish manufacturing industry. [**87 respondents**]
 [Gremyr et al, 2003]

To which extent is RD used in industry

Surveys

Swedish industry

[Gremyr et al, 2003]

UK industry

[Araujo, 1996]

US Industry & Military

[Thornton, 2000]

The extent of **use** of robust design methods in the Swedish manufacturing industry. [24 respondents]
 [Gremyr et al, 2003]

To which extent is RD used in industry

Experience from industry

- Testing
- Tolerance Analysis
- FMEA

Reasons

*“major part of research on RDM has focused on developing **statistical techniques**”.*

- Gremyr [2003]

*“**lack of quantitative models** that enable a design team to make quick and accurate decisions”*

*“that there is large body of literature but the tools are **too complex**”.*

- Thornton [2000]

*“**tools require experienced or trained staff**”*

- Araujo [1996]

*“Easier to use **testing, quality control and high-precision production** than analyses and simulations”*

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Some have success!

1. What have they done
2. What were the effects

4 case companies

1. Medical devices
2. Automotive
3. Defense
4. Aerospace

TQM&BE: How to implement and apply Robust Design: Insights from industrial practice

[Lars Krogstie, Martin Ebro, Thomas J. Howard – 2014]

	MEDICAL DEVICES	DEFENSE	AEROSPACE	AUTOMOTIVE
WHY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delays in late design stages Shorter and more predictable lead-time. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internal cost of poor quality Resources tied up in control and inspection. 	<p>Cost of Non-Quality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expensive “in service” changes Cost of redesign due to validation procedures. 	<p>Cost of Non-Quality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Avoid failures in market Maintain brand reputation.
HOW	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Defined roles and responsibilities Robustness Cockpit with 6 KPI's and requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gradual implementation of Six Sigma and DFSS-practices Defined System Engineer role. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training of engineers + chief design engineers Certification scheme with robustness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Toolbox of 15+ RD tools Training and coaching (after failed attempt using external trainers).
CHALLENGES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resistance to change RD seen as an add-on to existing development activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lacking adoption of RD-tools and methods Visualising the usefulness of DoE after to initial unsuccessful use. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Different perception of the novelty in the initiative The initial process towards RD was over-formalised. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unsuccessful ‘tool-pushing’ by external consultants No acknowledgement of need for change.
SUCCESS FACTORS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal qualities and competencies of chief / lead engineers Coaching and support of lead engineers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gradual implementation of Six Sigma practice Consistency in definitions of framework. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and courses focus on chief design engineers Having tools that are used on daily basis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engagement and training of middle management Transition from external “tool-pushers” to internally driven processes.
EFFECTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guidance on how to develop good designs Increased transparency for management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cross-functional collaboration Design reviews increased insight in design features. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More insight into their own design & understanding of the product behaviour Saved time in PD-process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stronger focus on knowledge and facts Increased understanding of the root causes of failures.

Training, roles and responsibilities

Substantial training – typically 5+ days for all engineers

Ongoing coaching and support from internal consultants

Dedicated roles and responsibilities:

- Chief engineer
- Lead engineer
- Belting system (green/black belts)

Processes, methods and tools

Integration into product development manual

	Medical Device	Defense	Aerospace	Automotive
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 KPI's • KPI's presented at gate review meetings. 	Cross-functional reviews	Projects required to use RD tools, but can choose which ones	Projects required to define strategy for dealing with variation and noise.
Tools	Specific procedure and tools for each KPI.	DfSS-tools	Toolbox with 40+ tools	Robust Design Toolbox (15+ tools) provided and supported

Success factors

	Medical Device	Defense	Aerospace	Automotive
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competencies of chief / lead engineers • Coaching and support of lead engineers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gradual implementation of Six Sigma practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and courses focus on chief design engineers • Having tools that are used on daily basis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement and training of middle management • Transition from external “tool-pushers” to internally driven processes.

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Effects

- Increased transparency for management

- Insight into own designs & root cause of failures
- Stronger focus on knowledge and facts
- Guidance on how to develop good designs
- Cross-functional Collaboration
- Fewer specs on drawings

- Fewer milestone delays
- Shorter product development time

Expected effects and how to measure them

- Shorter leadtime
 - Fewer milestone delays
 - Fewer mould iterations
 - Fewer QC resources
 - Fewer R&D resources
 - Verification
 - Improved First Time Yield
 - Reduced Customer Complaint Rate
 - Reduced number of Change Notes
 - Lower tolerance demand on production drawings
 - ...
- Comparable across product categories
 - Easy to gather data
 - Access to reliable historical data

Effect measurements

Effect measurements – first results

Summing up

- Why RD is necessary
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ISoRD14 Proposal

- How do we develop a Robust Design **paradigm** that will be **adopted by industry**?
- How do we measure and **quantify the effects** of Robust Design?

Questions and comments